

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT, JULY 1, 2020 – JUNE 30, 2021

A TURBULENT YEAR, AND A TRIBUTE TO CLIR'S STAFF

President's Message for the 2020-21 Annual Report

In looking ahead, institutions

and organizations often choose a guiding metaphor to characterize recent accomplishments and infer more of the same advancement in the years to come. “A beacon for change,” “a new road taken,” “a compass for the next decade” are typical descriptions of the symbolic navigational tools, highways, and methods of enlightenment we use to characterize our efforts. This rhetorical strategy requires a working environment over time that has a predictive continuity and familiarity to sustain such comparisons.

In this respect, the past two years confound expository practice. We are just beginning to grasp the immediate and longer-term effects and the adjustments needed to manage the likely sweeping changes ahead. But the effects will be deeply transformative on a global scale, requiring a more exacting accounting of what is under way and a more explicit reassurance of how our achievements can be carried forward into an opaque future.

CLIR, like other organizations, has sought meaningful responses to the COVID-19 pandemic and the inspiration of voices committed to social justice, broadly defined as a core tenet of the Black Lives Matter movement.

In so doing, the flexibility, dedication, and insight of CLIR's staff have been indispensable.

As the pandemic surged and confounded our national and international working environment, the exuberant professional colleagues who administer and manage our programs took early responsibility to keep them functional in a world where physical conferences and face-to-face social networking vanished overnight. In solidarity with Black Lives Matter and the systemic inequities confronting our colleagues who are Black, Indigenous, and people of color (BIPOC), CLIR's staff were similarly constitutive in accelerating our efforts to identify and reveal historically marginalized resources, archives, records, and stories, striving to integrate those voices into the larger national narrative, and providing nuance and complexity for a more accurate understanding of our historical context. Acknowledging their roles, it is to the Council's staff that this annual letter is dedicated.

THE PANDEMIC

As the COVID-19 virus surged, it was understood that CLIR's meetings and events had to become exclusively virtual. These included the review panels of Recordings at Risk and Digitizing Hidden Collections.

The panelists for these programs have always met in person: Building trust among the reviewers is critical, and social contact has been an expedient way to promote a sharing of ideas and perspectives. With thoughtful adjustments to the schedule and additional time allocated for topical challenges, the online formats proved efficient and well received. The largest, most complex undertaking has been to move the entire DLF Fall Forum online.

This entailed transposing a quarter-century tradition of in-person collaboration to a virtual space. With help from dozens of working group members and volunteers, the 2020 DLF Forum was fully accessible in its premier virtual instantiation, as was the adjacent NDSA Digital Preservation conference and 5 for 5: Conversations on Five Years of Digitizing Hidden Collections, which were also originally designed as physical gatherings. More threatening personal circumstances emerged as the pandemic closed borders and airports. Many CLIR fellows are working on dissertations in remote countries with limited connections. Staff worked diligently with funders to redirect grant resources that could safely extend each scholar's stay and assist them in traveling home once the borders reopened.

BLACK LIVES MATTER

As protests grew and drew broader attention to the pervasive, entrenched racism in American life and culture, from the blatant murder of people of color by white law enforcement agents to the more subtle codes of class hierarchies and the terms used to perpetuate them, a nation—or an encouraging cross-section of our nation—stirred. At CLIR, work begun in previous years to build programs that reveal and sustain historically marginalized voices that can then be heard and studied became especially timely.

Earlier internal conversations exploring the possibility of formalizing Digitizing Hidden Collections to focus on marginalized cultural expression were invigorated. In February 2021, a new iteration of the program, called “Amplifying Unheard Voices,” was announced. Similarly, our partnership with the HBCU Library Alliance was created in part to seek support for projects that would expose a wealth of rare archives and collections sequestered in selected HBCU libraries.

These collections, traditionally inaccessible, are pertinent to the African-American communities and to a more nuanced historical narrative. We are in a planning phase to prototype a hidden-collections-structured approach for neglected and suppressed resources intrinsic to our national identity, with HBCU library resources as the cynosure.

MISSION AND VALUES

In May 2021, CLIR began a vigorous review of our mission, purpose, vision, and values. We expect this effort, involving CLIR's staff, board of directors, and many supporters and alumni of CLIR's programs, to span much of the next year. We will assess our current circumstances and consider the more tumultuous landscape we are likely to tend in the next 5 to 10 years. The discussions will shape our evolving response in ways that exemplify our commitment to an ethical, just, and equitable commonwealth of shared knowledge. Such a review is requisite for any organization's health and sustainability while acknowledging that our reflections and final recommendations are today particularly urgent and consequential.

While no organization can claim to plot a predictive course in this era of uncertainty, we can affirm that CLIR's dedicated, empathetic personnel uniquely position us to continue to thoughtfully assess and manage the range of challenges, complexities, and opportunities we confront. We will continue to adapt, adjust, pivot when necessary, and anneal on behalf of our global community to arrive together, strengthened and wiser, in what will inevitably be a new place of different metaphors and signposts we will learn to follow.

Charles J. Henry, President

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DIGITAL LIBRARY FEDERATION	1
DLF Forum	
Working Groups	
GRANTS AND FELLOWSHIPS	3
Digitizing Hidden Collections	
Recordings at Risk	
Postdoctoral Fellowship Program	
Mellon Dissertation Fellowships	
PARTNERSHIPS	7
HBCU Library Alliance Partnerships	
Leading Change Institute	
Digital Library of the Middle East	
Iraqi Jewish Archive	
Kurdish Heritage Institute Digital Library	
Affiliates	
PUBLICATIONS AND RESOURCES	11
Material Memory	
New Publication Series	
Blog Highlights	
REVENUE AND EXPENSES	13
STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION	14
SPONSORS, MEMBERS, FUNDERS, GOVERNANCE, AND STAFF	15

DIGITAL LIBRARY FEDERATION

DLF FORUM

The annual Forum, DLF's signature event, took place Nov. 9–10, 2020. Because of the pandemic, the Forum was held virtually for the first time. Stacey Patton, journalist and professor at Howard University and Morgan State University, opened the event with a keynote, “Do Black Lives Matter in Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums?”

Two days of presentations, panels, tutorials, and lightning talks followed, covering topics that ranged from creating accessible and inclusive content to using geographic information systems tools for engagement.

The Forum was open to anyone who registered, free of charge, broadening the audience while benefiting those who were furloughed, unemployed, or without funding. More than 1,200 people from over 30 countries participated during the Forum's scheduled video releases and social events and via Slack chat channels. Recordings and transcripts for all Forum sessions are openly available on CLIRDLF's YouTube channel.

New this year was the presence of 11 community journalists—attendees from various backgrounds who were given stipends to share their voices and experiences on the DLF blog. NDSA's Digital Preservation 2020: Get Active with Digital Preservation followed the Forum on November 12.

The guiding focus for the 2020 Forum was building community while apart.

In June 2021, Jennifer Ferretti joined CLIR as DLF senior program officer, filling a leadership position that had been vacant since the departure of Bethany Nowviskie in 2019, and following the tenure of Louisa Kwasigroch as interim senior program officer. Formerly a digital initiatives librarian at the Maryland Institute College of Art on Piscataway land in Baltimore, she is also founder and principal of We Here, a community dedicated to supporting Black, Indigenous, and people of color in library and information science professions. In 2018, she was named a Library Journal Mover and Shaker.

FORUM VIRTUAL PHOTO BOOTH

Images from the 2020 CLIR events virtual photo booth

DLF WORKING GROUPS

DLF's 12 working groups represent a community of practitioners who collaborate year-round to solve problems in a variety of digital library subfields, from project management and assessment to labor and accessibility.

Working groups are organized across institutional and geographical boundaries, and participation is open to anyone, regardless of institutional affiliation.

The following exemplify the range of activity undertaken by the working groups:

- In November 2020, DLF's Born Digital Working Group received the Software Sustainability Institute Award for Research and Innovation in recognition of the working group's document, *Levels of Born Digital Access*. The document provides a tiered set of format-agnostic practices to facilitate and improve access to born-digital materials across five areas: accessibility, description, researcher support and discovery, security, and tools.

- In late 2020, the DLF Digital Library Pedagogy group issued a call for proposals for its #DLFteach Toolkit 2.0. The toolkit focuses on lesson plans to facilitate disciplinary and interdisciplinary work engaged with 3D technology. The first instructional resources were shared in October 2021.
- The Digital Accessibility Working Group is creating a how-to manual for accessible information technology policies and workflows.

GRANTS AND FELLOWSHIPS

DIGITIZING HIDDEN COLLECTIONS

In March 2021, CLIR announced the award of just over \$4 million to 16 projects proposed during the 2020 award cycle of the Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives program. The program supports digitizing collections of rare and unique content in collecting institutions. The awarded projects cover subjects ranging from hip-hop, fashion, and public media to plant specimens and whale reproduction. Announcement of the awards, typically made in early January, was delayed until spring because of the pandemic's impact on application and review activities.

Workplace and service closures caused by the pandemic also created challenges for projects that had been funded in recent years but were not yet completed. In response, staff designed and launched an opportunity to apply for small emergency relief supplementary grants. The grants provided funds to adapt project plans to accommodate remote and other safe working conditions. CLIR awarded \$122,281 to 18 organizations in December 2020.

In March 2021, CLIR launched a new iteration of the grant program, called Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives: Amplifying Unheard Voices (DHC-AUV). The program focuses on projects to digitize materials that deepen public understanding of the histories of people of color and other communities and populations whose work, experiences, and perspectives have been insufficiently recognized.

Digitizing Hidden Collections

5 for 5: Conversations on Five Years of Digitizing Hidden Collections, held in conjunction with the DLF Forum. 2020 marked the fifth year of CLIR's Digitizing Hidden Collections program. To showcase work being done, CLIR sponsored a free online event in November 2020 that featured five presentations representing more than 20 funded projects. Some 400 viewers attended. Planning is under way for an in-person event in conjunction with the DLF Forum in late 2022 for grant recipients to share lessons from their project work.

The new program expands eligibility to include Canadian nonprofit institutions, which were previously allowed to participate only as supporting partners to US-based institutions. Recipients of the 2021 award cycle will be announced in April 2022.

Following the new program's launch, CLIR commissioned two researchers to conduct an external assessment of the DHC-AUV initiative. With expertise in digital archives and community-based research, the team will help CLIR create inclusive, equitable, and broadly accessible regranting initiatives that serve a diverse range of organizations. The study will run concurrently through the first full application and review cycle as researchers gather data from applicants, reviewers, and staff.

RECORDINGS AT RISK

Currently in its fifth year, CLIR's Recordings at Risk grant program supports the digital preservation of rare and unique audio, audiovisual, and other time-based media of high scholarly value.

In April 2021, CLIR awarded \$552,905 to 17 projects that preserve materials ranging from radio and television broadcasts to oral histories, music recordings, films, and performance videos.

As in the Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives program, staff designed and launched an opportunity for grant recipients who were adversely affected by the pandemic to apply for small emergency relief supplementary grants.

The grants provided funds to adapt previously approved work plans to accommodate remote and other safe working conditions. CLIR awarded \$20,991 to seven recipient organizations in December 2020.

POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM

In summer 2020, CLIR welcomed eight postdoctoral fellows as the seventeenth cohort in the Postdoctoral Fellowship Program.

Top row (left to right): Portia D. Hopkins, Luling Huang, Petrouchka Moise, Jennifer Ross. Bottom row (left to right): Synatra Smith, Francena Turner, Laura Wilson, Rebecca Pickens. Not pictured: Elisa Tersigni

Fellowships offer recent PhD graduates the chance to develop research tools, resources, and services while exploring new career opportunities at host institutions that include libraries, archives, and museums.

In academic year 2020–2021, fellows worked in one of three areas: (1) data curation for African American and African Studies funded by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation; (2) data curation for the energy social sciences supported by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation; and (3) digital humanities and digital scholarship funded by individual host institutions.

In January 2021, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation awarded CLIR \$2.01 million to extend Data Curation Fellowships in African American and African Studies. The funds support current fellows whose work was negatively affected by the global pandemic by enabling them to extend their time at host institutions by up to two years.

On September 1, 2020, CLIR appointed program alumni Jennifer Garcon and Emily Beagle as co-faculty for the 2020–2021 Postdoctoral Fellowship Program. Both previously held fellowships created with the support of the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation.

Emily Beagle (left) and Jennifer Garcon (right)

In late 2020, fellows initiated a new CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship writing project focusing on the possibility of a third library—a space within or outside institutions that challenges what we have come to know about the libraries of the past. The project, which encompasses podcasts, essays, and a visualization, will be published in early 2022.

In February 2021, CLIR published Capacity Assessment of Latin American and Caribbean Partners: Report of Symposium and Recommendations by CLIR fellows Hadassah St. Hubert, Jennifer Isasi, Nicté Fuller Medina, and Margie Montañez.

The report was based on a virtual symposium held in April 2020 that engaged stakeholders from institutions in Latin America and the Caribbean in a discussion of strategies for digital archiving and cultural preservation and identification of common areas of need. The report is available in English, French, Haitian Kreole, Portuguese, and Spanish.

With the support of The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR initiated in 2019 an external evaluation of the Postdoctoral Fellowships in Data and Software Curation, with a particular focus on the humanities-oriented data curation fellowships created since 2013. The study's primary goal is to determine the value that the fellows' work in data curation holds for scholarship and academic library practice.

Additional goals are to identify which aspects of the fellowship experience have the greatest influence on fellows' career choices and to trace the effects of the fellowships on participating host institutions' staffing, resources, and service strategies.

The study will also explore the effects of the pandemic and remote working, the economic crisis, and movements highlighting racial injustice on the fellowships, the fellows, and host institutions. A report of findings will be published in 2023.

MELLON DISSERTATION FELLOWSHIPS

The CLIR-Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Source Research Program awarded its final round of fellowships in spring 2019. Funded by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation since 2002, the program has supported 258 fellows, who together represent 59 US universities. These fellows have conducted research at more than 1,700 sites in 86 countries worldwide.

They have worked with original materials of every sort, from handwritten and illuminated manuscripts, ancient pottery, and medieval paintings to early films and vinyl LPs; from medical, corporate, and prison records to political pamphlets from flea market bins.

In pursuit of their research, these scholars have traveled the globe, becoming experts in scholarly research both in the United States and across national borders, often working in settings with very different approaches to cultural heritage and information management.

To celebrate and reflect on the program's two decades, CLIR will host a symposium for alumni in early 2022 to share lessons learned through the dissertation research fellowships. The symposium will focus on the evolution of original source research since the program's inception and consider what the future may hold for archives and researchers.

Fellows will discuss how broad global changes have affected original source research and the risks facing researchers and collections today. They will also consider the role that archives and archival research will play in addressing the social, political, and environmental challenges of the coming decades.

PARTNERSHIPS

HBCU LIBRARY ALLIANCE PARTNERSHIP

In July 2019, CLIR and the HBCU Library Alliance announced a long-term partnership to foster awareness of and access to the history and collections held by HBCU institutions.

In late 2020, the two organizations received a grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation for a project to identify common values, priorities, and needs for describing and managing special and archival collections for HBCU Library Alliance members.

In spring 2021, three researchers began conducting interviews and focus groups to help the HBCU Library Alliance envision how its 76 member institutions can work together to preserve, describe, and digitize their unique collections. Final reports are expected in early 2022.

At the 2020 virtual DLF Forum, during two partner sessions, staff who work in and with HBCU libraries spoke about ongoing digital library and archives work, initiatives, and programs. The sessions, which featured six presentations, were co-organized by the HBCU Library Alliance and DLF.

Image of early faculty at South Carolina State University, "The Early Beginnings of SC State University," presented at the 2020 Virtual DLF Forum

LEADING CHANGE INSTITUTE

The Leading Change Institute (LCI), cosponsored with EDUCAUSE, brings together information sector leaders, including deans, librarians, and information technologists, who seek to advocate for and advance change in today's rapidly evolving higher education environment.

Each summer, a weeklong residential institute is held for a new cohort of participants who learn from and discuss current events with colleagues from academia, associations, grant-making agencies, industry, and government. After attending the institute, participants join other alumni in monthly chats.

The COVID-19 pandemic forced postponement of what would have been the 2020 LCI.

New LCI logo enamel pin created for LCI alumni

In response, deans Joanne Kossuth and Elliott Shore increased the frequency of the monthly LCI alumni Zoom meetings to once per week and invited members of the 2020 class to participate. This helped to engage the new class and served as a way for alumni from all years to support one another and exchange strategies for leading their departments during a challenging time. With the rise in vaccinations and the loosening of restrictions in Washington, DC, CLIR was able to hold an in-person institute July 12–16, 2021.

In July 2020, CLIR and Stanford Libraries announced the release of a public, open platform for the Digital Library of the Middle East (DLME), which aims to become one of the world's largest online archives of Middle Eastern and North African artifacts.

A partnership with Qatar National Library, the DLME aggregates, through an ongoing program, digital records of published materials, documents, maps, artifacts, audiovisual recordings, and more from the Middle East and North Africa region.

DIGITAL LIBRARY OF THE MIDDLE EAST

Since the launch, the portal has grown to more than 150,000 objects in over 100 collections from 35 institutions from around the world. It also provides an array of applications, tools, and descriptions that enrich the content and facilitate browsing, searching, and interpretation.

Glazed crouching lion
Iraq, ca. 1500 BCE
The Penn Museum

IRAQI JEWISH ARCHIVE

Startling evidence of the once-vibrant Jewish life in Iraq came to light in May 2003, when more than 2,700 books and tens of thousands of documents were discovered by a US Army team in the flooded basement of Iraqi intelligence headquarters.

Tik (Torah case) from Baghdad, 19th-20th century

The remarkable survival of this written record of Iraqi Jewish life provides an unexpected opportunity to better understand this 2,500-year-old Jewish community. For centuries, it flourished in what had generally been a tolerant, multicultural society. But circumstances changed dramatically for Jews in the mid-twentieth century, when most Iraqi Jews fled and were stripped of their citizenship and assets.

To provide accessibility to the damaged books and documents, the US National Archives and Records Administration (NARA) and its partners preserved, cataloged, and digitized these materials. NARA also managed an initial series of exhibitions.

In 2020, CLIR signed a memorandum of understanding with the US Department of State to collaborate on an enhanced exhibit and related activities built around the story of Jews in Iraqi society and how, in diaspora, they carried their Iraqi heritage with them around the world.

Although COVID paused much of the momentum for planning a traveling exhibit and website redesign, a meeting was held in March 2021 to discuss the future of the physical collection.

Organized by the State Department and the American Jewish Committee, the meeting brought together key stakeholders to discuss the concerns of the members of the Iraqi Jewish diaspora.

CLIR outlined its current draft prospectus, developed with the State Department for a traveling exhibit of the collection, as well as ideas for refocusing the current site (<https://ijarchive.org>) and expanding the content with lesson plans, additional oral histories, and more content to tell the history of the Jewish community in Iraq.

KURDISH HERITAGE INSTITUTE DIGITAL LIBRARY

A yearlong collaboration between CLIR and the Kurdish Heritage Institute (KHI) in Slemani, in the Kurdish Federal Region of Iraq, came to fruition in February 2020 with the introduction of the first fully functional digital library in Kurdistan and Iraq.

KHI Website

Project co-directors Amed Demirhan and Peter Herdrich led the effort with support from CLIR and KHI staff. In 2019, the US Embassy in Baghdad chose CLIR from among more than 20 applicants to lead its Digitization of the Kurdish Heritage Institute Collection project.

The project had dual goals. The first was to create digital records of the KHI collections to secure and preserve information about the objects.

The second was to use those records to build a functional digital library so that the collections could be shared and used.

The first year was spent in providing equipment, training the team to document and digitize collection materials, and processing thousands of books on Kurdish culture. After one year, CLIR received a grant extension to fund cataloging and publishing of the records to the KHI website using Omeka.

AFFILIATES

CLIR establishes collaborative relationships and cross-institutional initiatives with organizations that have similar missions in the pursuit of common goals. The affiliates program allows CLIR to serve as a fiscal or administrative home for mission-aligned organizations that may not need to be independent legal entities.

Affiliates have their own governance and mission, while CLIR provides integrated services and access to tools, platforms, research, and expertise to reduce costs, create greater efficiencies, and enable affiliates to better serve their constituencies.

The logo for the International Image Interoperability Framework (iif), consisting of three stylized human figures in blue and red.

International
Image
Interoperability
Framework

The logo for the International Internet Preservation Consortium (IIPC), featuring a stylized green and red graphic to the left of the text "IIPC" in a bold sans-serif font, with "netpreserve.org" in a smaller font below it.

INTERNATIONAL
INTERNET
PRESERVATION
CONSORTIUM

The logo for Weave, featuring a blue circular icon with a white stylized "W" inside, next to the text "Weave" in a serif font.

PUBLICATIONS AND RESOURCES

MATERIAL MEMORY

In fall 2019, CLIR launched season one of a new podcast, *Material Memory*. In theme-based seasons, *Material Memory* explores the effects of our changing world—from digital technologies to the climate crisis—on our ability to access the record of our shared humanity, and the critical role that libraries, archives, museums, and other public institutions play in keeping cultural memory alive.

SEASON ONE

Season one celebrates the United Nations–designated Year of Indigenous Languages. In each of six episodes, host Joy Banks speaks with people involved in the work of restoring audio and audiovisual recordings of indigenous languages and their often-Herculean efforts to make these recordings accessible to the communities they represent.

Inupiat child

SEASON TWO

Season two, released in November 2020 and hosted by Nicole Kang Ferraiolo, explores the impact of the climate crisis on communities and their cultural heritage. The eight episodes take a critical look at the role of information and cultural heritage professionals in responding to the crisis and consider how different approaches to preservation can help or harm affected communities.

Baul gaan musicians of Bangladesh

SEASON THREE, LAUNCHING IN 2022

Season three, planned for release in early 2022, will spotlight people and collections in libraries at six HBCUs and offer insights on these cornerstones of culture and historical knowledge.

NEW PUBLICATION SERIES

In June 2021, CLIR issued a call for proposals for a new publication series, "Pocket Burgundies," modeled on its "burgundy reports," so named for their cover color.

The series invites ideas on topics relating to established areas of CLIR publication—digital libraries, preservation, emerging technologies, and trends in information use—as well as proposals on topics in the information field(s) relating to social and racial justice, labor, accessibility, sustainability, building and maintaining community, and more.

The series will depart from CLIR's traditional reports in that they will be shorter; the ideas will be generated by the community; and submissions will be reviewed by an editorial committee. Four proposals will be funded in the first year and will be announced in December 2021.

CLIR BLOG HIGHLIGHTS

YEAR OF CLIR

In January 2020, CLIR initiated a weekly series, Year of CLIR, highlighting a key activity from each year since its founding in 1956.

COVID (RE)COLLECTIONS

In March 2020, CLIR started the COVID (Re)Collections blog series to help people in the information field process COVID-19 and share their responses as the situation evolved. From April 2020 to July 2021, 23 blog posts were published, sharing perspectives of authors in a range of institutions around the country.

REVENUE AND EXPENSES

REVENUE SOURCES

EXPENSES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

AS OF JUNE 30, 2021

CURRENT ASSETS	UNRESTRICTED	TEMPORARILY RESTRICTED	TOTAL JUNE 30, 2021
Cash and cash equivalents	\$1,827,548	\$9,725,255	\$11,552,803
Investments	\$519,694		\$519,694
Prepaid expenses	\$231,290		\$231,290
Employee retention credit receivable	\$38,419		\$38,419
Accounts receivable	\$2,578	\$2,232,197	\$2,234,775
Total Current Assets	\$2,619,529	\$11,957,452	\$14,576,981
TOTAL ASSETS	\$2,619,529	\$11,957,452	\$14,576,981

CURRENT LIABILITIES

Accounts payable	\$242,239	\$242,239
Deferred registration revenue	\$131,740	\$131,740
Accrued expenses	\$106,596	\$106,596
Total Current Liabilities	\$480,575	\$480,575
TOTAL LIABILITIES	\$480,575	\$480,575

NET ASSETS	\$2,138,954	\$11,957,452	\$14,096,406
TOTAL LIABILITIES AND NET ASSETS	\$2,619,529	\$11,957,452	\$14,576,981

SPONSORS, MEMBERS, FUNDERS, GOVERNANCE, AND STAFF

AS OF JUNE 30, 2021

The following provide crucial financial support for the activities and programs of the Council on Library and Information Resources. Institutions are invited to sponsor CLIR and/or join DLF at any point in the year.

CLIR Sponsors and DLF Members

American University	Lehigh University*	The Huntington Library, Art Museum, and Botanical Gardens+	University of Tennessee*
Amherst College*	Library of Congress*	The Obama Foundation+	University of Texas at Arlington*
Arizona State University*	Los Alamos National Lab+	The Ohio State University*	University of Texas at Austin*
Atlanta University Center*	Marquette University*	Tufts University*	University of Toronto*
Auburn University	Massachusetts Institute of Technology*	Tulane University*	University of Victoria*
Bates College*	McGill University Libraries+	Union College*	University of Virginia*
Baylor University*	McMaster University*	University at Albany*	University of Washington*
Beloit College	Metropolitan New York Library Council+	University at Buffalo*	University of Wisconsin-Madison*
Berea College	Miami University	University of Arizona*	University of Wyoming*
Bibliotheca Alexandrina+	Michigan State University+	University of Arkansas Libraries, Fayetteville*	Ursinus College
Boston College*	Middle Tennessee State University*	University of British Columbia, Vancouver*	Vassar College*
Bowdoin College*	Montana State University*	University of Calgary*	Villanova University*
Brigham Young University	Mount Holyoke College*	University of California, Berkeley*	Virginia Commonwealth University
Brown University*	National Archives and Records Administration+	University of California, Irvine*	Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University*
Bryn Mawr College*	National Gallery of Art+	University of California, Los Angeles*	Wake Forest University*
California Digital Library*	National Library of Medicine*	University of California, Riverside+	Washington and Lee University*
California Polytechnic State University	New York Art Resources Consortium+	University of California, San Diego*	Washington University*
Carleton College	New York Public Library*	University of California, Santa Barbara*	Wayne State University+
Carnegie Mellon University*	New York University*	University of California, Santa Cruz+	Wellesley College
Carthage College	North Carolina State University*	University of Chicago*	Wesleyan University*
Casalini Libri S.p.A.	Northeastern University*	University of Cincinnati	West Virginia University*
Clemson University+	Northwestern University*	University of Colorado at Boulder*	Whitman College+
Coalition for Networked Information	Oberlin College*	University of Delaware*	Williams College*
Colgate University*	Occidental College*	University of Denver*	Wilson College
College of Charleston	Oregon State University*	University of Georgia*	Yale University*
College of the Holy Cross	Peabody Essex Museum Phillips Library+	University of Houston*	
Colorado College+	Pennsylvania State University*	University of Idaho+	Foundation, Institutional, and Individual Support
Colorado State University+	Philadelphia Museum of Art+	University of Illinois at Chicago*	The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
Columbia University Libraries*	Preservation Technologies	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*	The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
Concordia University+	Princeton Theological Seminary+	University of Iowa+	David Rumsey
Connecticut College	Princeton University*	University of Kansas*	EDUCAUSE
Cornell University*	Purdue University*	University of Kentucky+	Institute of Museum and Library Services
Corning Museum of Glass+	Qatar National Library*	University of Louisville+	Library of Congress
Council of Independent Colleges	Reed College*	University of Maryland at College Park*	Samuel H. Kress Foundation
Dartmouth College*	Rhodes College*	University of Massachusetts Amherst*	
Duke University*	Rice University*	University of Miami*	
Emory University*	Rockefeller Archive Center+	University of Michigan*	
Florida Atlantic University Library	Rockefeller University*	University of Minnesota*	
Florida State University+	Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey	University of Nebraska-Lincoln*	
Furman University	San Diego State University	University of Nevada, Las Vegas+	
George Mason University	Science History Institute+	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill*	
Georgetown University*	Sewanee, The University of the South	University of North Carolina at Greensboro+	
Georgia Institute of Technology*	Skidmore College*	University of North Texas*	
Georgia Public Library Service+	Smith College*	University of Notre Dame*	
Georgia State University+	Smithsonian Institution*	University of Oklahoma	
Getty Research Institute+	Southern Methodist University*	University of Oregon	
Grand Valley State University+	St. Olaf College	University of Ottawa	
Grinnell College*	Stanford University*	University of Oxford*	
Hamilton College*	Stony Brook University*	University of Pennsylvania*	
Harvard University*	Swarthmore College*	University of Pittsburgh*	
Haverford College*	Syracuse University*	University of Richmond*	
HBCU Library Alliance	Temple University*	University of Rochester*	
Indiana University*	Texas Christian University	University of South Carolina+	
Internet Archive+	The Catholic University of America	University of South Florida*	
Iowa State University*	The Claremont Colleges Library*	University of Southern California*	
ITHAKA+	The Clark Art Institute		
Jisc			
Johns Hopkins University^			
Kenyon College*			
Lafayette College*			
Lake Forest College			

^ Sustaining sponsor/member
* CLIR sponsor and DLF member
+ DLF member only

BOARD MEMBERS

Edward Ayers
Tucker-Boatwright
Professor of the Humanities and
President Emeritus
University of Richmond

Guy Berthiaume (Vice Chair)
Librarian and Archivist of Canada
Emeritus

Michele Casalini
Chief Executive Officer
Casalini Libri

Christopher Celenza
Dean of Georgetown College
Georgetown University

Dan Cohen
Dean of Libraries and Vice Provost
for Information Collaboration
Northeastern University

Tess Davis
Executive Director
Antiquities Coalition

Kurt De Belder
University Librarian, Director of
the Leiden University Libraries,
and Director of Leiden University
Press
Leiden University

Kathleen Fitzpatrick
Director of Digital Humanities
and Professor of English
Michigan State University

Fenella France
Chief, Preservation Research and
Testing Division
Library of Congress

Charles Henry
President
CLIR

Michael A. Keller
Vice Provost and University
Librarian, Publisher of Stanford
University Press, and Vice Provost
for Teaching and Learning
Stanford University

W. Joseph King
Former President
Lyon College

Carol Mandel
Dean Emerita
New York University Division of
Libraries

Max Marmor
President
Samuel H. Kress Foundation

Buhle Mbambo-Thata (Chair)
University Librarian
National University of Lesotho

Asma Naeem
Chief Curator
Baltimore Museum of Art

Richard Ovenden
Bodley's Librarian
University of Oxford

Sandra Phoenix
Executive Director
HBCU Library Alliance

Winston Tabb
Dean of University Libraries
Johns Hopkins University

Ben Vinson III
Provost and Executive Vice
President
Case Western Reserve
University

Sohair Wastawy
President
The Information Guild

John Price Wilkin (Treasurer)
Dean of Libraries and University
Librarian
University of Illinois at Urbana-
Champaign

STAFF

Lizzi Albert
Deputy Operations Officer

Joy Banks
Program Officer

Sharon Burney
Program Officer

Nicole K. Ferraiolo
Director of Global Strategic
Initiatives

Jennifer Ferretti
Senior Program Officer, DLF

Wayne Graham
Chief Information Officer and
Director of Informatics, Cultural
Networks, and Knowledge Systems

Josh Hadro
Managing Director, IIF
Consortium

Charles Henry
President

Olga Holownia
Senior Program Officer,
IIPC

Sharon Ivy Weiss
Chief Financial Officer

Louisa Kwasigroch
Managing Director

Amy Lucko
Chief Operating Officer

Erin O'Donnell
Outreach and Engagement
Associate

Megan O'Hearn
Community and Event
Coordinator, IIF Consortium

Alyson Pope
Grants and Contracts Manager

Becca Quon
Program Officer

Diane Ramirez
Administrative Services Manager

Jodi Reeves Eyre
Program Officer

Aliya Reich
Program Manager for
Conferences and Events

Gayle Schechter
DLF Program Associate

Kathlin Smith
Senior Director of
Communications

Christa Williford
Senior Director of Research
and Assessment

PRESIDENTIAL FELLOWS

Kevin FitzGerald
Retired Vice President and
Chief of Staff
University of North Carolina
at Chapel Hill

Fenella France
Chief, Preservation Research
and Testing Division
Library of Congress

David Gift
Associate Vice President for
Community Engagement
Internet2

Jacqueline Goldsby
Professor of English and African
American Studies
Yale University

Carol Mandel
Dean Emerita, New York
University Libraries

Herman Pabbruwe
Retired CEO
Koninklijke Brill N.V.

Elizabeth Waraksa
Associate Dean, Libraries and
Academic Innovation
The George Washington
University